

Ya Sin (Q36:13-30) — Dr. Mustafa Khattab, The Clear Quran translation.

36:13 Give them an example 'O Prophet' of the residents of a town, when the messengers came to them.

36:14 We sent them two messengers, but they rejected both. So, We reinforced 'the two' with a third, and they declared, "We have indeed been sent to you 'as messengers'."

36:15 The people replied, "You are only humans like us, and the Most Compassionate has not revealed anything. You are simply lying!"

36:16 The messengers responded, "Our Lord knows that we have truly been sent to you.

36:17 And our duty is only to deliver 'the message' clearly."

36:18 The people replied, "We definitely see you as a bad omen for us. If you do not desist, we will certainly stone you 'to death' and you will be touched with a painful punishment from us."

36:19 The messengers said, "Your bad omen lies within yourselves. Are you saying this because you are reminded 'of the truth'? In fact, you are a transgressing people."

36:20 Then from the farthest end of the city a man came, rushing. He advised, "O my people! Follow the messengers.

36:21 Follow those who ask no reward of you, and are 'rightly' guided.

36:22 And why should I not worship the One Who has originated me, and to Whom you will be returned.

36:23 How could I take besides Him other gods whose intercession would not be of any benefit to me, nor could they save me if the Most Compassionate intended to harm me?

36:24 Indeed, I would then be clearly astray.

36:25 I do believe in your Lord, so listen to me."

36:26 'But they killed him, then' he was told 'by the angels', "Enter Paradise!" He said, "If only my people knew

36:27 of how my Lord has forgiven me, and made me one of the honourable."

36:28 We did not send any soldiers from the heavens against his people after his death, nor did We need to.

36:29 All it took was one 'mighty' blast, and they were extinguished at once.

36:30 Oh pity, such beings! No messenger ever came to them without being mocked.

— Dr. Mustafa Khattab, The Clear Quran

<https://quran.com/36/13-30>